

INNOVATION AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING
METHODOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS IN
TEACHING BASED ON THE PIRLS INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAM

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the development of methodological training of future primary school teachers in the teaching process based on the international assessment program PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study). The article analyzes the integration of innovative and information technologies into the educational process, improving the pedagogical competencies of teachers, as well as modern approaches to assessing students' reading literacy.*

The role and importance of information technologies in the training of teachers within the framework of the PIRLS program, as well as the renewal of teaching methods, are discussed and practical recommendations are given. The article is aimed at high-quality training of future generation teachers and facilitating their professional development.

Keywords: *PIRLS, modern approach, competence, teacher, student, technology, development, integration, methodology, global problem, literacy.*

Today, as a result of the reforms being implemented globally in the education system, the importance of international assessment programs, including the PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) program, is increasing. This program helps to identify the achievements and shortcomings of students in the educational process by assessing their reading literacy.

Based on the results of international assessments, it becomes possible to improve the quality of education in countries, improve the pedagogical activities of teachers, and revise curricula. In Uzbekistan, training primary school teachers based on the requirements of the PIRLS program is also one of the urgent issues.

In the world, effective technologies for improving the methodological preparation of teachers for teaching based on the international assessment program PIRLS - (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) are being implemented in the educational process.

Training pedagogical personnel in line with the requirements of the time, developing mechanisms for improving the professional and methodological preparation of future primary school teachers based on the international assessment programs (PIRLS), creating multimedia electronic resources based on international assessment programs, and assessing the quality of teaching are being carried out on a large scale. Along with such work, work is being carried out on "improving the process and tools for assessing the quality of education, implementing mechanisms that allow determining the achieved results", assessing the level of knowledge of students based on international standards, and implementing trends in improving the quality of teaching reading literacy subjects.

In recent years, in our republic, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" (No. PF-5712) dated April 29, 2019,

five initiatives have been implemented, including comprehensive measures aimed at creating additional conditions for the education of young people. A normative framework is being created for improving teaching methodologies, as well as for the gradual introduction of the principles of individualization in the educational process, as well as for the training, retraining and advanced training of professional personnel, the introduction of modern information and communication technologies and innovative projects in the field of public education, and participation in international research on assessing the quality of education. "To create a total of 769 video lessons for the electronic professional development platform by 2026 to train teachers in new methodologies according to the national curriculum" was identified as a key priority. This will expand the opportunities for future primary school teachers to improve their methodological training based on new pedagogical technologies and international assessment programs during the educational process.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", No. PF-4708 dated May 7, 2020 "On measures to improve the quality of education and develop scientific research in the field of mathematics", No. PQ-3775 dated June 5, 2018 "On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in the comprehensive reforms being implemented in the country", No. PQ-2909 dated April 20, 2017 "On measures to further develop the higher education system" and Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers dated December 8, 2018 This dissertation will serve as a practical guide to the implementation of the tasks set out in Resolution No. 997 "On measures to organize international research in the field of assessing the quality of education in the public education system," as well as other regulatory and legal documents related to this area.

The training of future teachers based on the requirements of this program will help them develop modern and effective teaching skills for students, as well as acquire internationally competitive knowledge and skills. This thesis analyzes the improvement of the methodological training of future teachers within the framework of the PIRLS program, the effectiveness of teaching based on modern pedagogical approaches and technologies.

The development of teaching methodologies for future primary school teachers based on the PIRLS assessment program involves the use of innovative and information technologies, including interactive teaching methods, digital textbooks and teaching and control systems.

These technologies will help teachers understand assessment criteria, develop students' reading literacy, and analyze assessment results.

Innovation and Information Technology

- **Interactive and Multimedia Tools:** To prepare for PIRLS, teachers can use interactive whiteboards, video tutorials, teaching and learning programs, and online platforms in the classroom. This helps to attract students' attention and deepen their understanding of the subject.

- **Digital textbooks and teaching materials:** Electronic textbooks and teaching materials (e.g., reading texts, questions and answers, assignments) adapted to PIRLS requirements enrich the educational process.

- **Teaching and learning systems:** These systems allow teachers to assess students' reading literacy, monitor their progress, and analyze results. With the help of these systems, teachers can improve their teaching methods.

- **Using technology in the classroom:** Tablets, computers, and other technical devices can be used in the classroom to prepare for PIRLS.

Information technologies for student assessment: In preparation for PIRLS, information technologies for student assessment (e.g., online tests, programming platforms) can help teachers more accurately assess student knowledge.

Ways to develop methodological preparation

Trainings and seminars: It is necessary to conduct special trainings, seminars and master classes for teachers on the PIRLS assessment program and its use.

Online courses: Online courses and webinars can be offered to help teachers strengthen and update their knowledge.

Exchange of experience: Best practices in PIRLS preparation can be promoted by organizing forums and sessions for teachers to share their experiences.

Use of assessment systems: Through the regular use of assessment systems adapted to PIRLS, teachers will have the opportunity to evaluate and improve their teaching methods.

The PIRLS international assessment program highlights the importance of innovative and information technologies in developing the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers. The integration of these technologies into the educational process will help increase the professional competencies of teachers and, as a result, further improve the reading literacy of students. We need to work on updating and improving the education system, because the future generation needs quality education.

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